

MusicPhone Tasks

MusicPhone is an application that runs on a GPS-enabled, MP3-capable mobile phone. MusicPhone will make recommendations for artists the user may like and find upcoming concert events for artists using data gathered from the Last.FM website. The goal of the following tasks is to implement the necessary logic to enable MusicPhone to make recommendations and plan a travel itinerary to concert events.

Task A: Ramp-up

A1. Run the project (Select the project, right click and Run As->Java Application, then select **App - app**), and see three UI windows appear. The Player and GPS UIs are complete. The Recommender window is just a skeleton. You will implement the required functionality in the `Recommender` class.

A2. Run SmokeTest (Select the project, right click and Run As->JUnit Test) and see the green bar. Check the structure of the sample test in `SmokeTest.java` to get familiar with the application.

A2. Take 5-10 minutes to review the information in the provided documentation.

Task B: Compute distance to a concert

The user will see how far away upcoming concert events are for a particular artist based on the user's current GPS position and the position of the concert's venue. Implement a public method with the signature `public static double computeDistance (GeoPoint, GeoPoint, String)` to calculate the great-circle distance between two geo-coded positions. A geo-coded position is represented by a `GeoPoint` object that specifies a latitude and longitude *in degrees*. The method computes the great-circle distance between two points in either kilometres ("km") or miles ("mi") as specified by the third parameter. Valid latitude values are between -90 and 90 *degrees*; valid longitude values are between -180 and 180 *degrees*. Sometimes a `GeoPoint` has an invalid latitude or longitude. In these cases, the distance returned should be `null`.

Examples:

<i>GeoPoint₁</i>		<i>GeoPoint₂</i>		<i>units</i>	Great-circle distance (in <i>units</i>)
<i>LatR₁</i> <i>LatD₁</i>	<i>LonR₁</i> <i>LonD₁</i>	<i>LatR₂</i> <i>LatD₂</i>	<i>LonR₂</i> <i>LonD₂</i>		
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>6.283</i>	<i>6.283</i>	km	0
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>360</i>	<i>360</i>		
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>1.047</i>	<i>0</i>	km	6671.70
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>60</i>	<i>0</i>		
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>6.283</i>	<i>6.283</i>	mi	0
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>360</i>	<i>360</i>		
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>1.047</i>	<i>0</i>	mi	4145.60
<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>60</i>	<i>0</i>		
<i>0.630</i>	<i>-1.513</i>	<i>0.592</i>	<i>-2.066</i>	mi	1793.55
<i>36.12</i>	<i>-86.67</i>	<i>33.94</i>	<i>-118.40</i>		

Numbers in roman type are in degrees.

Numbers in italics are in radians.

The formula for the great-circle distance is:

LonD = longitude in degrees;

LatD = latitude in degrees;

LonR = longitude in radians;

LatR = latitude in radians;

$$\text{radians} = (\text{degrees} \times \pi) / 180; \quad a = \sqrt{\sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\text{LatR}}{2}\right) + \cos(\text{LatR}_1) \times \cos(\text{LatR}_2) \times \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\text{LonR}}{2}\right)};$$

Great Circle Distance = $2 \times \arcsin(\min(1.0, a)) \times \text{Radius}$; where *Radius* is the Earth's radius in kilometers (6371.01) or in miles (3958.76).

Task C: Find concerts for an artist

Implement the `getDestinationsForArtist` method of the `Recommender` class. When the user clicks on an artist's name in the list of recommended artists, the UI calls the `getDestinationsForArtist` method to obtain a list of destinations, where each destination contains the info of an upcoming concert together with the distance to the concert's location from the user's current position. The user's current position is provided by the GPS. If the concert's location has an invalid `GeoPoint`, then the distance should be marked as `null`. You'll need to use `IConnector`'s `GetConcertForArtist` method to implement this task.

Task D: Recommend artists

Implement the `getRecommendations` method of the `Recommender` class. `MusicPhone` recommends artists based on the favourite artists of Last.FM users who are the top fans of the currently-playing artist on the user's player. `MusicPhone` recommends the 20 most-frequently-appearing artists among those fans' top artists (as in "people who like this artist also like these other artists..."). `getRecommendations` should return a list of `Recommendation` objects. Each `Recommendation` object consists of an artist's name (`artist`) and the frequency of occurrence (`fanCount`) of that artist. You will need to use `IConnector`'s `getTopFansForArtist` and `getTopArtistsByFan` methods to implement this method.

Example: Suppose the currently playing artist is *Cher*. Suppose *John*, *Sally*, and *Tom* are the only top fans of *Cher*. If *Tom* and *John* both like *U2* as well, then `getRecommendations` should return a list that includes a recommendation containing *U2* with a `FanCount` of 2.

Task E: Compute an itinerary for concerts

E0. Implement the `buildItineraryForArtists` method of the `Recommender` class. In the UI, the user can click on buttons that will add or remove a selected artist to a list of artists who the user would like to see in concert. Whenever this list is changed, the application recalculates an itinerary of upcoming concerts by calling this method. An itinerary is a list of `Destinations`, where each destination contains the concert information and the distance from the previous destination. The first destination's distance is the distance from the user's current position. The itinerary must be chronologically ordered according to the start date of the concerts in it. Satisfy the following constraints in any order, but tackling them *one by one*:

- E1.** The itinerary starts with the concert having the earliest start date for any of the selected artists.
- E2.** An artist has at most one concert in the itinerary (some artists may have no concerts, however).
- E3.** No two concerts in the itinerary may take place on the same day.
- E4.** If multiple artists have concerts on the same day, the itinerary includes only the concert that is closest in distance to the previous destination.
- E5.** If the same artist has multiple concerts on the same day, the itinerary includes only the concert that is closest in distance to the previous destination.